

A Study of Uterine Fibroids and Its Degenerative ChangesNeelam Gupta¹, Anuj Kamboj², Amit Joon³, Ritika Kansal⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, G.S Medical College and Hospital,²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, N.C Medical College and Hospital³Associate Professor, Department of community medicine, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Sciences,⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Sciences

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Abstract:**Background:** Uterine fibroids or myomas or leiomyoma of uterus are the most common type of benign tumor of uterus and also most common pelvic tumor in women. They may have unusual presentations in the form of location or undergo various degenerative changes posing great diagnostic difficulties.**Aim:** To identify the various secondary degenerative changes and histopathological variants of uterine leiomyomas.**Material and Methods:** The study included a total of 120 cases of leiomyomas diagnosed in the department of pathology for a period of six months. Detailed gross and microscopic examination was carried out and the data recorded.**Results:** Out of total 120 cases of leiomyoma, intramural was the most common (51.6%) location. Age of the patients ranged from 18-60 years with peak incidence in 41-50 years (38.3%). Secondary changes were observed in 16(13.3%) cases. Out of which hyaline degeneration was the most common type of degeneration and observed in 68.75% cases. Other secondary changes observed were myxoid degeneration, calcific degeneration, hydropic degeneration and hemorrhagic infarction. Only 1 cases of cellular leiomyoma were identified as histological variant.**Conclusion:** Leiomyomas of female genital tract are common benign tumors. Degenerative changes are more common in intramural leiomyomas. Secondary changes and histological variants may pose diagnostic difficulties.A complete gross and histological examination is mandatory to rule out malignant transformation.

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Introduction

Uterine fibroids or myomas or leiomyoma of uterus are the most common type of benign tumor of uterus and also most common pelvic tumor in women. [1] In women by the age of 35 incidences of fibroids is 60% and over 80% by the age of 50. [2] They originate from myometrial smooth muscle cells. [3,4] Exact etiology is not known but the cause estimated to be is estrogen and progesterone which proliferate tumor growth as fibroid rarely occur before menarche and reduces after menopause. [5,6]

Risk factors for developing fibroids are age, early age at menarche, reduced fertility, frequent alcohol and caffeine consumption, obesity, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, previous pelvic inflammatory disease. [7] While decreased exposure to estrogen found with smoking, exercise and increased parity is protective. [8]

The uterine fibroids are classified into three categories according to their anatomical location: submucous fibroids- located in the muscle below the endometrium; interstitial/intramural fibroids are

most common and located within the uterine wall; and subserous fibroids located just below the serosal surface of the uterus. Uterine leiomyomas may undergo various secondary degenerative changes such as hyaline, myxoid, cystic, fatty or red degeneration and dystrophic calcification. Hyaline degeneration is the most common secondary degenerative change while malignant transformation to leiomyosarcoma, if it occurs at all, is extremely rare. [9] Histological variants of leiomyoma are cellular leiomyoma, atypical leiomyoma, and epithelioid leiomyoma. Some of these variants exhibit diagnostic difficulty then it becomes problematic to differentiate them from low grade leiomyosarcoma.

Material and Method

A prospective and observational study was conducted over a period of six months from January 2023 to June 2023 in the department of pathology of tertiary care hospital and Medical College. The institutional ethical committee clearance was taken.

Inclusion Criteria: All women diagnosed with fibroid (non-pregnant cases) admitted for treatment of fibroid at our tertiary care hospital and those willing to participate in the study after due written consent were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Hysterectomy specimens in which fibroid was not observed either on gross or on microscopy were excluded out.

The patient’s demographic data, clinical history and type of surgical procedure were recorded. The surgical specimens were first fixed in 10% buffered formalin for at least 24 hours after slicing them. Detailed gross examination was noted including size, location, number and secondary changes in leiomyoma. Representative tissue sections were taken including the leiomyoma and other associated pathologies. If leiomyomas were multiple in numbers then tissue sections were taken from each leiomyoma. Sections were processed using

automated tissue processor and embedded in paraffin wax. 3-5 µm thick sections were cut and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin. The sections were examined under light microscope for features like cell type, pattern, cellularity, crowding, nuclear atypia, mitoses (per 10HPF) and presence of secondary degenerative changes like hyaline degeneration, calcification, cystic and red degeneration.

Results

We included total 120 women with the confirmed diagnosis of uterine fibroid in our study.

Out of 120 women, majority were from 40-50 years age group i.e. 46 (38.3%) followed by 40 (33.3%) from 30-40 years, 30 (25%) from above 50 years and 4 (3.3%) from 21-30 years age group (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution according to age group

Age group in year	Frequency	Percent
<20	0	0.0
21-30	4	3.33
31-40	40	33.3
41-50	46	38.3
>50	30	25
Total	120	100

Majority of the women were from urban area i.e. 81% and remaining 19% were from rural area (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution according to place of residence

Complaints of the patients revealed abdominal lump in 45%, abnormal uterine bleeding in 30.83%, metrorrhagia in 27.5%, weakness in 29.16%, infertility in 20.83%, menorrhagia in 20.83%, pelvic pain in 19.16%, dysmenorrhoea in 10%, urine retention in 606% (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution according to complaints/symptoms

Complaints	Frequency	Percent
Abnormal uterine bleeding	37	30.83
Menorrhagia	25	20.83
Metrorrhagia	33	27.5
Dysmenorrhoea	12	10
Abdominal lump	54	45

Pelvic pain	23	19.16
Urine retention	8	6.66
Weakness	35	29.16
Infertility	25	20.83

Intramural leiomyoma was the most common site accounting for 62(51.6%) cases followed by sub serosal in 38(31.6%) cases and submucosal in 20(16.6%) cases. (Table 3)

Table 3: Distribution according to type of fibroid

Type of fibroid	Frequency	Percent
Intramural	62	51.6
Submucosal	20	16.6
Subserosal fibroid	38	31.6

In 11(9.1%) cases leiomyomas were present in more than one location in the uterus. Secondary changes were observed only in 16(13.3%) cases of all leiomyomas.

Most of the changes were present in intramural leiomyomas. Hyaline degeneration was the most common observation and found in 11(68.75%) of these cases. Other secondary changes included

myxoid degeneration in 2(12.5%), calcific degeneration in (12.5%), hydropic or cystic degeneration in (6.25%).

Among the variants of leiomyoma, only 1(6.25%) case of cellular leiomyomas was observed with increased cellularity, closely packed spindle cells some of which showed overlapping, scant mitotic figure and absence of necrosis. (Table 4)

Table 4: Secondary changes in leiomyomas

Secondary changes	Number	Percentage
Hyaline degeneration	11	68.75
Myxoid degeneration	2	12.5
Calcific degeneration	2	12.5
Hydropic/cystic degeneration	1	6.25
Total	16	100

Discussion

Uterine leiomyomas are the most common benign neoplasm which arises from the smooth muscles of the myometrium. Hysterectomy is the most common gynecological surgery and leiomyomas are found to be the most common clinical finding accounting for about 80% of all hysterectomy specimens. Other common causes of hysterectomy include adenomyosis, prolapse uterus, dysfunctional uterine bleeding and rarely malignancy. [10]

The most common symptom in our study was abnormal uterine bleeding. Few presented with lower abdominal pain and dysmenorrhea, correlating with the findings of other studies. [11,12] The cause of abnormal uterine bleeding in fibroids may be due to increased vascularity, enlargement of the endometrial surface and altered uterine contractility. [13] These causes are assumed to be due to being estrogen dependent.

Uterine leiomyomas are classified according to the location into intramural, submucosal and sub serosal types. Majority of the leiomyomas in our study were intramural 62(51.6%) followed by sub serosal 38(31.6%) and submucosal 20(16.6%). These findings were similar with other studies by Gowri et al [12] and Abraham J et al. [14] uterine leiomyomas

can be found in more than one location in the same hysterectomy specimen. 11 cases (9.1%) had leiomyoma in more than one location, mainly comprising of intramural and sub serosal types.

In our study hyaline degeneration was the most common secondary change and found in 11(68.7%) cases similar to the studies by Begum et al [15] and Dayal et al [11]. In our study, most commonly observed symptoms are abdominal mass (45%) followed by abnormal uterine bleeding (30.83%) In various studies conducted by Buttran et al and Okolo et al showed that vast majority of leiomyomas are asymptomatic and most common symptom of uterine leiomyoma is abnormal uterine bleeding. [16-18]

Conclusion

Uterine leiomyomas are the most common benign tumor of female genital tract. Although symptoms depend on size and location of leiomyoma, various symptoms are associated with certain degenerative changes which can be life threatening. Now a day, these conditions are being more common in young female, so a detailed study can be helpful for the clinicians also to assess early complications and manage accordingly. Although leiomyomas are benign, they are associated with significant

morbidity in women of reproductive age group. Early diagnosis and introduction of new minimally invasive management of fibroids can avoid hysterectomy in young patients who wish to preserve their fertility. Secondary degenerative changes and variation in morphology can also present as diagnostic challenge.

Ethical approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

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